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Research Article

**A GOLD STANDARD INVESTIGATION
ESOPHAGODUDENOSCOPY TO DETERMINE THE UPPER
GASTROINTESTINAL BLEEDING ETIOLOGY AND FOR
VARICEAL BLEEDING SOCRRING*****Dr. Zain Fatima, **Dr. Muhammad Zeeshan Riaz, ***Dr. Qurat-ul-ain Hameed*****Aziz Fatimah Hospital, Faisalabad******Allied Hospital, Faisalabad*******Govt M Nawaz Sharif Teaching Hospital Yakki Gate, Lahore****Abstract**

Objective: To confirm the upper gastrointestinal bleeding etiology validity for determining variceal bleeding by doing esophagoduodenoscopy as gold standard.

Study Design: A cross validation survey.

Place and Duration: In the Gastroenterology Department of Allied Hospital, Faisalabad for one year duration from June 2017 to June 2018.

Methods: A total of 120 patients with 53 males and 67 females with age above than 18 years having upper Gastrointestinal Bleeding were included. SPSS (version 17) was used to access and analyze data and the mean and standard deviation were calculated for quantitative variables such as age and frequency and gender were calculated for qualitative variables.

Results: The results of the analysis showed that the vast majority of patients were between 51 and 60 years 30.83, the mean and standard deviation were recorded as 35.64 + 7.75 years, 55.83% (n = 67) women, 44.17% (n = 53) male patient, esophagoduodenoscopy as gold standard (the frequency of bleeding varicose) in 13.33% (n = 16) was recorded as the gold standard while no variceal bleeding in 86.67 of patients (n=104). 78.57, 95.28%, calculated as the sensitivity, correct positive predictive value Determination of the bleeding varicose veins while performing esophagoduodenoscopy validity of the etiology of ulcer, anxiety, upper gastrointestinal bleeding score as indicated by the negative predictive value and accuracy rate, respectively 68.75%, 97.12% and 93.33%.

Conclusion: The results of the study are valid in gold standard, and in patients with upper gastrointestinal bleeding, significant specificity and sensitivity was determined by determining the etiology of the bleeding by performing esophagoduodenoscopy as highly as the etiology score

Key words: Etiological score, upper gastrointestinal bleeding, variceal bleeding.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Zain Fatima,**

Aziz Fatimah Hospital, Faisalabad.

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Upper gastrointestinal bleeding is a common gastroenterology emergency and having 5 to 14% of mortality rate. Upper gastrointestinal hemorrhage is determined as bleeding derived from a close source of the Treitz ligament. The incidence of upper gastrointestinal bleeding is approximately 100 cases per 100,000 inhabitants per year. Cardinal properties are black tar-like stool hemememesis (vomiting blood) and melena (passage). The most common causes of upper gastrointestinal bleeding are duodenal ulcer (35%) and gastric ulcer (20%). esophageal varices are the most common cause of portal hypertension, which may develop in patients with portal hypertension. Endoscopic subsequent appropriate endoscopic treatment significantly reduces the mortality and the need for transfusion, cost of hospital stay and medical care. For this reason, patients are mostly managed for a long time before being referred to esophagoduodenoscopy at the center with the facilities available. To determine the etiology of hemorrhage, vericeal clinical parameters increase the clinical gain of upper gastrointestinal bleeding while considering varices, and decide the empirical treatment of upper gastrointestinal bleeding; it has been developed to score the etiology. In a recent study, the etiology of the upper gastrointestinal bleeding showed that the score has a sensitivity and specificity of 85% to 81% to predict the bleeding score. The result of this study may be useful in diagnosing the cause of gastrointestinal bleeding, such as variceal bleeding or non-variceal bleeding, providing specialized treatment of esophagoduodenoscopy for non-specialized upper gastrointestinal bleeding providing empirical treatment and avoiding delay according to incomplete treatment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This cross validation survey was conducted in the Gastroenterology Department of Allied Hospital, Faisalabad for one year duration from June 2017 to

June 2018. All patients were included in 18 years of age with upper gastrointestinal bleeding. Upper non-collaborative / patient history of upper gastrointestinal bleeding were not included presented after 72 hours of bleeding in the upper GI; The patient met the selection criteria and the patient explained the nature and the proposed work and informed consent was sought. In the guidance of Performa structure, information about clinical factors were collected and examined. Based on the variables listed in the form, the etiology of the upper gastrointestinal bleeding was calculated for each case if the score was 3.1 means bleeding present and if the score was below 3.1 than no bleeding. To determine the chronic liver disease (spider nevus, Palmer erythema, gynecomastia, bruise, acid, ankle edema, splenomegaly, confusion, testicular atrophy and sleep) score if more than two points it means positive case and not present if 0, the red vomitus is present if score 1 and 0 if not there scored. Upper gastrointestinal hemorrhage and upper endoscopy in all patients within 72 hours after varicose vein upper gastrointestinal bleeding, to detect out of varicose veins as the cause of bleeding. SPSS (version 17) was used to analyze and access data and the standard deviation and mean were recorded for quantitative variables such as age and frequency and gender were recorded for qualitative variables.

RESULTS:

120 patients who met the exclusion / exclusion criteria were included in the analysis to determine the validity of the esophagoduodenoscopy for hemorrhage scoring system as a total gold standard, or the etiology of the upper gastrointestinal bleeding. The age distribution of the patients is shown in Table 1, and the majority of patients, 37 (30.83%), were between 51-60 years old, 27 (22.5%) were between 41-50. only 11 years (9.17%) age, 23 (19.17%) -40 between 31 years of age, 22 (18.33%), 18-30 years of age > 60 years, mean and the standard deviation was recorded as 35.64 + 7.75 years (Table 1).

Table 1: Age Distribution (n=120)

Age(in years)	n	%
18-30	11	9.17
31-40	23	19.17
41-50	27	22.5
51-60	37	30.83
>60	22	18.33

Mean and sd 35.64+7.75

The distribution of patients by gender was 67 (55.83%) females and 53 (44.17%) males (Table 2).

Table 2: Gender Distribution (n=120)

Gender	n	%
Male	53	44.17
Female	67	55.83

The variceal bleeding (gold standard esophagoduodenoscopy) was recorded in 16 (13.33%) while in 104 (86.67%) no variceal bleeding (Table 3).

Table 3: Frequency of variceal bleeding (on esophagoduodenoscopy as gold standard) (n=120)

Variceal Bleeding	n	%
Yes	16	13.33
No	104	86.67

11 (9.17%) true positives, 5 (4.17%) false positive three (2.5%) false negative occur, while performing an esophagoduodenoscopy such as gold standard to determine the bleeding of the gastrointestinal bleeding validity score and 101 (84.17%), true negative, specificity, sensitivity, negative predictive value, positive predictive value and accuracy rate were calculated as 78.57, 95.28%, 68.75%, 97.12% and 93.33% (as calculated in Table 4).

Table 4: Validity of Upper Gastrointestinal Bleeding Etiology Score for Determining Variceal Bleeding by Doing Esophagoduodenoscopy as Gold Standard

Variceal Bleeding	Non-Variceal bleeding	Total
Upper Gastrointestinal Bleeding Score >3.1		
True positive(a) 11(9.17%)	False positive (b) 5 (4.17%)	a+b 16(13.33%)
Upper Gastrointestinal Bleeding Score <3		
False negative(c) 3 (2.5%)	True negative (d) 101 (84.17%)	C ⁺ d 104 (86.67%)

Sensitivity= 78.57%

Specificity= 95.28%

Positive predictive value= 68.75%

Negative predictive value= 97.12%

Accuracy rate=93.33%

DISCUSSION:

Upper gastrointestinal bleeding (upper GIS bleeding, for its abbreviation in English) is a frequent gastrointestinal emergency and has a mortality rate of 14% to 5%. The causes of upper GIS bleeding are classified as (esophageal and gastric varices) and bleeding. Out of varices (erosive gastroduodenitis, peptic ulcer, tumor, reflux esophagitis, vascular ectasia, etc.) are the other causes. At present (briefly EGD) emergency esophagogastroduodenoscopy is the standard choice for active upper GI hemorrhage research because it provides the diagnosis and treatment of upper GI bleeding. Lack of unofficial

services, inadequate endoscopists and well-trained medical teams and equipment is a issue. For this reason, most patients generally receive medical treatment for some time before being referred to EGD at centers with existing facilities. By applying esophagoduodenoscopy as a gold standard can determine the validity of the upper gastrointestinal bleeding etiology score for the determination of varices, and this can be used to diagnose the cause if found satisfactory, so this study has been planned is not lacking facility for esophagoduodenoscopy varices or upper gastrointestinal bleeding as out of varicosity, upper gastrointestinal bleeding empirical

providing treatment and preventing delay in terms of specific treatment. The results of the study revealed that the majority of patients, 30.83% (n = 37), 51 and 60 years, mean and standard deviation were recorded as 35.64 + 7.75, 55.83% (n = 67) female, 44.17% (n = 53) male patients. The result of the study is consistent with a recent study showing that the etiological score of upper gastrointestinal bleeding has a sensitivity of 85% and a specificity of 81% to estimate the bleeding score. Therefore, the <3.1 score will help to exclude variceal bleeding with confidence. Although little work has been done to diagnose the cause of upper gastrointestinal bleeding, there is no local study on this issue, so the results of the study can be considered as a primary, and more studies are needed to achieve greater confidence in this etiological score for the diagnosis of morbidity.

CONCLUSION:

At the end of the study, it was determined that the etiology score was valid for the determination of variceal bleeding by esophagoduodenoscopy as the gold standard and it had a significant specificity and sensitivity in patients with upper gastrointestinal bleeding.

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